

A NOTE ON CHANGES IN RELIGIOUS AFFILIATION OF EASTERN ORTHODOX IN AUSTRALIA 2006 TO 2021

James A Athanasou

Independent Researcher, athanasou@optusnet.com.au

Abstract

The purpose of this report is to summarise the number of Eastern Orthodox in Australia from 2006 to 2021. The analysis covers all the groups listed officially under the heading of Eastern Orthodox is the official Census data. The total number of Eastern Orthodox increased by 6.4% from 502,799 in 2016 to 535,459 in 2021.

Keywords

Eastern Orthodox, Australia, census

I. INTRODUCTION

This report documents the number of Eastern Orthodox in Australia from 2006 to 2021. The findings are derived from the five-yearly national census and in response to the optional question on one's religion.

By way of background, the category of Eastern Orthodox is a heterogeneous group. It comprises: Albanian Orthodox, Antiochian Orthodox, Greek Orthodox, Macedonian Orthodox, Romanian Orthodox, Russian Orthodox, Serbian Orthodox and Ukrainian Orthodox.

At the last 2021 Census, Eastern Orthodox numbered just over half a million and made up 2.1% of the population. An earlier report (Athanasou, 2022) documented the number of Eastern Orthodox as a proportion of the population. It reached its peak at 2.89% in 1981 and has not been increasing remarkably, although individual groups within this cohort (e.g., Greek Orthodox, Serbian Orthodox) have different trajectories.

By far the largest group within the Eastern Orthodox cohort is Greek Orthodox at around 390,963. The breakdown across the groups from 2006 to 2021 is shown in Table 1.

The statistics are not perfect. For a start, the question is optional. Also, one expects that there is possibly some sampling error in the year-to-year variations due to incomplete data, incorrect categorisation (e.g., "Orthodox" versus Greek Orthodox). There have been some changes in the Census classifications where the Orthodox nfd (not formally defined) has altered from 2006-2011 to 2016-2021 (Australian Bureau of Statistics, 2022).

II. RESULTS

The core groups in the Eastern Orthodox category in Australia are Greek Orthodox (73% - all percentages rounded) followed

by Macedonian Orthodox (10%) and Serbian Orthodox (9%). The breakdown across groups is illustrated in Figure 1

TABLE 1

Eastern Orthodox in Australia: 2006-2021

Group	2006	2011	2016	2021
Eastern Orthodox, nfd	48158	49577	1181	1365
Albanian Orthodox	72	47	44	16
Antiochian Orthodox	7830	8265	9841	14264
Greek Orthodox	374575	383401	373589	390963
Macedonian Orthodox	48083	52051	49683	52311
Romanian Orthodox	1607	1882	1925	2147
Russian Orthodox	19969	22251	21961	22631
Serbian Orthodox	39968	41834	41015	48287
Ukrainian Orthodox	2978	2713	2742	2627
Eastern Orthodox, nec	917	1066	818	848
Total	544163	563072	502799	535459

Note: nfd=not formally defined; nec = not elsewhere classified

Figure 1. Eastern Orthodox 2021 (excludes Eastern Orthodox not elsewhere classified or defined)

Antiochian Orthodox showed the greatest proportional increase (82%) from 2006 to 2021, followed by Romanian Orthodox (34%), then Serbian Orthodox (21%), Russian Orthodox (13%), Macedonian Orthodox (9%) and Greek Orthodox (4%).

III. CONCLUSIONS

Despite the commonly assigned title of the category “Eastern Orthodox”, it was beyond the remit of this paper to canvass the theological, ecclesiastical as well as canonical issues of membership in this grouping. The main purpose has been to describe the status from 2006 to 2021.

In that regard, the numbers of Eastern Orthodox in the general population may look small at just over half a million, when compared with Catholics (4.9 million) or Anglicans (2.49 million) but they still represent a unique and significant grouping amongst Christians in Australia. It also represents a large workload for the various Eastern Orthodox groups.

As for the future, it is not known how the increasing secularisation of ideas and behaviour will affect Orthodox numbers in Australia. It is not yet clear whether younger generations will gravitate away from their religion. The rate of conversion to Orthodoxy may also play a role. Finally, the age profile of the Orthodox population comprising some older immigrants will also have an impact as will birth rates.

One thing is certain: as migrant churches, the Eastern Orthodox brought a multicultural dimension to the panorama of Christianity in Australia, which was Anglo-Celtic in origin. With changes in the patterns of migration, the multicultural presence of other non-English speaking and non-Christian backgrounds (Hindu, Islam, Buddhism) is now asserting itself.

Notwithstanding these broader changes, within the Eastern Orthodox, the large Greek, Macedonian and Serbian influence seems likely to persist. It already accounts for 491,594 out of the existing 535,470 Eastern Orthodox. There will be variations in trajectories of the groups over time but without further influence the positions or ranking of the groups within the overall category of Eastern Orthodox seem to have stabilised.

Funding Preparation of this report received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial or not-for-profit sectors.

REFERENCES

- Australian Bureau of Statistics. (2022, July 4). *Religious affiliation in Australia*. ABS. <https://www.abs.gov.au/articles/religious-affiliation-Australia>.
- Athanasou, James. (2022, 4 October). A 2021 UPDATE ON GREEK ORTHODOX IN AUSTRALIA. Zenodo. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7151379